

Conductometric Studies on Mn (II)- Thiosemicarbazone Systems

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Abstract Thiosemicarbazone complexes processes potential biological implications. These complexes also have therapeutic importance. Present research describes the conductometric investigations on few Mn (II)- thiosemicarbazone complexes. The conductometric studies have been carried out in doubly distilled water, Triton X-100 and Brij-35 mediums. Association constants and formation constants have been calculated and different types of stoichiometry [M : L] have been observed for metal-ligand complexes as; 1: 2, 1: 3, 1: 4 etc.

Keywords Mn (II)-Thiosemicarbazone, Association Constants, Formation Constants, Triton X-100.

Introduction Thiosemicarbazones have received considerable attention because of their binding ability with metal ions and for their antitumour, antiprotozoal, antibacterial or antiviral activities [1].

Objective of study In this paper we are reporting the association constant, Gibbs Free energies of Mn (II) complexes with thiosemicarbazide based ligand: 3, 4, 5-Trimethoxybenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone [3, 4, 5-TBT]

Review of Literature Anticarcinogenic, antibacterial, anti-HIV, fungicidal, antiviral, antifungal and antitumour properties etc. have been reported involving transition metal ions with thiosemicarbazones [2]

Methodology All the chemicals used were of AR grade and procured from Himedia. Metal salt were purchased from E. Merck and were used as received. All solvent used were of standard/spectroscopic grade. Ligand 3, 4, 5-TBT was synthesized by condensation reaction of thiosemicarbazide with benzaldehyde in presence of methanol according to the literature [3]. Metal-ligand complexes were formed by conductometrically. Conductivity TDS Meter 307 is employed in present study for conductometric investigations.

Tools Used The conductometric titration of the ligand (1x10⁻³) mole/L in doubly distilled water, TX-100 and Brij-35 medium against the MnCl₂ (1x10⁻⁴) mole/L was performed with definite amount of metal (MnCl₂) solution [4,5]. The cell was calibrated with standard KCl solution [6].

Result and Discussion In all three medium the values of molar conductance were calculated at 298.15 K temperature. [7]

The mediums were water, Brij-35 and TX-100 medium/m = (K_s-K_{solv})/K_{cell} x 1000/C
------(1)

K_s = specific conductance of the solution, K_{solv} = specific conductance of the solvent, K_{cell} = cell constant, C = molar concentration of the metal ion solution.

The stoichiometric of complexes were decided by association and formation constants. The association constants of complexes were calculated by using equation (2) [8,9] in water, TX-100 and Brij-35 medium.

$$K_A = [I_0^2 (I_0 - I_m)] / [4Cm^2 \gamma_{\pm}^2 / m^3 S(Z)] \quad \text{-----} (2)$$

K_A = association constants, I_m = molar conductance, I₀ = limiting molar conductance of metal ion solution, γ_± = activity coefficient, S(Z) = Fuoss-Shedlovsky factor [10]

Association constants (K_A) and gibbs free energy (ΔG_A) of Mn(II) with [3, 4, 5-TBT] were calculated in different medium (water, Triton X-100 and Brij-35)

Figure-a

Figure-b

Figure-c

Plot of molar conductance Vs M/L ratio

Graph have been plotted between molar conductance and M/L ratio in water , TX100 and Brij 35 medium (figure a, b and c respectively) .

The Gibbs free energies were obtained by employing equation (3) [11]

$$\Delta G_A = - R T \ln K_A \text{ ----- (3)}$$

here

R = gas constant (8.314 J), T = absolute temperature

The result of Gibbs free energies were calculated.

$$K_f = [\Lambda_M - \Lambda_{obs}] / [(\Lambda_{obs} - \Lambda_{ML})[L]] \text{ ----- (4)}$$

The formation constants (K_f) [12,13] of complexes were calculated by applying above eq.

here,

Λ_M = molar conductance of the metal ion solution alone, Λ_{obs} = observed molar conductance of solution,

Λ_{ML} = molar conductance of the complex

The calculated values (K_f) for complexes are presented in Tables (i-v).

Also the Gibbs free energies of complex formation constant were obtained using equation (5) and exhibited in

tables(i-v).

$$\Delta G_f = - RT \ln K_f \text{ ----- (5)}$$

Table- (i)-Formation constants and Gibbs free energies of formation for 1:3 (M/L) Mn(II) complexes in water medium

Λ_{obs}	[L]	$(\Lambda_M - \Lambda_{obs})$	$(\Lambda_{obs} - \Lambda_{ML})[L]$	K_f	ΔG_f (kJ/mol)
64	0.000632911	7	0.001164557	6010.869565	-21.53676406
64	0.000625	7	0.00115	6086.956522	-21.56789797
64	0.000617284	7	0.001135802	6163.043478	-21.59864512
65	0.000609756	6	0.001731707	3464.788732	-20.1731802
65	0.00060241	6	0.001710843	3507.042254	-20.20318194
66	0.000595238	5	0.002285714	2187.5	-19.03489463
66	0.000588235	5	0.002258824	2213.541667	-19.06418625
66	0.000581395	5	0.002232558	2239.583333	-19.09313527
67	0.000574713	4	0.002781609	1438.016529	-17.99659802
67	0.000568182	4	0.00275	1454.545455	-18.02488534
67	0.000561798	4	0.002719101	1471.07438	-18.05285301

67	0.000555556	4	0.002688889	1487.603306	-18.0805082
67	0.000549451	4	0.002659341	1504.132231	-18.1078578
67	0.000543478	4	0.002630435	1520.661157	-18.13490848

$$l_{ML} = 62.16 \text{ Cm}^2\text{Ohm}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$$

Table-(ii)-: Formation constants and Gibbs free energies of formation for 1:3 (M/L) Mn(II) complexes in water medium

/obs	[L]	(/M-/obs)	(/obs-/ML)[L]	K _f	Δ G _f (k J/mol)
60	0.000847458	11	0.004076271	2698.544699	-19.55455279
61	0.000833333	10	0.004841667	2065.404475	-18.8927408
62	0.000819672	9	0.005581967	1612.334802	-18.27979692
62	0.000806452	9	0.005491935	1638.76652	-18.32004355
63	0.000793651	8	0.006198413	1290.653009	-17.72899755
63	0.00078125	8	0.006101563	1311.139565	-17.76797652
63	0.000769231	8	0.006007692	1331.62612	-17.80635113

$$l_{ML} = 55.19 \text{ cm}^2\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$$

Table - (iii)-: Formation constants and Gibbs free energies of formation for 1:3 (M/L) Mn(II) complexes in TX-100 medium

/obs	[L]	(/M-/obs)	(/obs-/ML)[L]	K _f	Δ G _f (k J/mol)
55	0.000735294	12	0.001367647	8774.193548	-22.49934222
55	0.000735294	12	0.001367647	8774.193548	-22.49934222
55	0.000735294	12	0.001367647	8774.193548	-22.49934222
55	0.000735294	12	0.001367647	8774.193548	-22.49934222
56	0.000735294	11	0.002102941	5230.769231	-21.21757104
56	0.000735294	11	0.002102941	5230.769231	-21.21757104
56	0.000735294	11	0.002102941	5230.769231	-21.21757104
56	0.000735294	11	0.002102941	5230.769231	-21.21757104
56	0.000735294	11	0.002102941	5230.769231	-21.21757104
57	0.000735294	10	0.002838235	3523.316062	-20.23836783

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57	0.000735294	10	0.002838235	3523.316062	-20.23836783
57	0.000735294	10	0.002838235	3523.316062	-20.23836783
57	0.000735294	10	0.002838235	3523.316062	-20.23836783
57	0.000735294	10	0.002838235	3523.316062	-20.23836783
57	0.000735294	10	0.002838235	3523.316062	-20.23836783
57	0.000735294	10	0.002838235	3523.316062	-20.23836783

$$/_{ML} = 53.14 \text{ cm}^2\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$$

Table (iv)-: Formation constants and Gibbs free energies of formation for 1:4 (M/L) Mn(II) complexes in TX-100 medium

/obs	[L]	(/M-/obs)	(/obs-/ML)[L]	K _f	Δ G _f (k J/mol)
51	0.000769231	16	0.0008	20000	-24.54102476
52	0.000757576	15	0.001545455	9705.882353	-22.74941707
52	0.000746269	15	0.001522388	9852.941176	-22.78668121
53	0.000735294	14	0.002235294	6263.157895	-21.663927
53	0.000735294	14	0.002235294	6263.157895	-21.663927
53	0.000735294	14	0.002235294	6263.157895	-21.663927
54	0.000735294	13	0.002970588	4376.237624	-20.77556941
54	0.000735294	13	0.002970588	4376.237624	-20.77556941
54	0.000735294	13	0.002970588	4376.237624	-20.77556941
54	0.000735294	13	0.002970588	4376.237624	-20.77556941

$$/_{ML} = 49.96 \text{ cm}^2\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$$

Table (v)-: Formation constants and Gibbs free energies of formation for 1:2 (M/L) Mn(II) complexes in Brij-35 medium

/obs	[L]	(/M-/obs)	(/obs-/ML)[L]	K _f	Δ G _f (k J/mol)
61	0.000568182	18	0.000568182	31680	-25.65068975
61	0.000561798	18	0.000561798	32040	-25.67865743
61	0.000555556	18	0.000555556	32400	-25.70631261

61	0.000549451	18	0.000549451	32760	-25.73366221
61	0.000543478	18	0.000543478	33120	-25.76071289
61	0.000537634	18	0.000537634	33480	-25.78747114

$$i_{ML} = 60 \text{ cm}^2\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$$

Conclusion

The negative values of ΔG show the ability of the studied ligand to form stable complexes by conductometric. The ΔG values were found negative which prove that stable metal ligand complexes were obtained by conductometric method.

References

- [1] Maqbool, S. N., Lim S. C., Park K. C., Hanif R., Richardson D. R., Jansson P. J., et al. (2020), Overcoming tamoxifen resistance in oestrogen receptor-positive breast cancer using the novel thiosemicarbazone anti-cancer agent : DpC. *Br. J. Pharmacol.* Vol.177, No.10, pp 2365–2380.
- [2] Dharmasivam, M., Azad, M. G., Afroz, R., Richardson, V., Jansson., P. J., Richardson, D. R. (2022), The thiosemicarbazone, DpC, broadly synergizes with multiple anti-cancer therapeutics and demonstrates temperature- and energy-dependent uptake by tumor cells: *Biochim. Biophys. Acta. Gen. Subj.* Vol. 1866, No. 8, pp 130152.
- [3] Latika, D., Singh, R. V., (2011), Synthesis, Spectroscopic Characterization, Antimicrobial, Pesticidal and Nematicidal Activity of Some Nitrogen-Oxygen and Nitrogen-Sulfur donor Coumarins based Ligands and their Organotin(IV) Complexes: *Appl. Organomet. Chem.*, Vol. 25, pp. 643-652.
- [4] Lobana, T. S., Sanchez, A., Casas, J. S., (1997), Synthesis, Characterization, and In vitro Cytotoxic Activities of Benzaldehyde Thiosemicarbazone Derivatives and Their Palladium (II) and Platinum (II) Complexes Against Various Human Tumor Cell Lines : *Journal of the Chemical Society*, Vol. 22, pp 4289- 4300.
- [5] Rathore, U., Gupta, R., Soni, M., Bhojak, N., (2016), Conductometric and pH Metric Investigations on Thiosemicarbazone Co(II) Systems: *International Journal of New Technologies in Science and Engineering*, Vol. 3 No. 3, pp 1-10.
- [6] Gomaa, E. A., Jahdali, B. M. A., (2011), Association of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ With Kryptofix-221 in Mixed (MeOH-DMF) Solvents at Different Temperatures: *American Journal of Fluid Dynamics*, Vol. 1 No.1, pp 4-8.
- [7]. Biswa, R., Brahman, D., (2009), Thermodynamics of the Complexation between Salicylaldehyde Thiosemicarbazone with Cu(II) Ions in Methanol–1,4-Dioxane Binary Solutions: *Indian Journal of Chemistry*, Vol. A No. 48, pp 1145.
- [8] Gryzybkowski, W., Pilarczyk, M., (1989), Electrical Conductance and Apparent Molar Volumes of $\text{Al}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$, $\text{Be}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ in N, N-Dimethylformamide Solutions at 25°C : *Electrochimica Acta*, Vol. 32, pp1601-1605.
- [9] Shishtawi, N. A. E., Hamada, M. A., (2010), EAGomaa, Influence of Permanent Magnet on the Association Constants of FeCl_3 in 50% Ethanol- H_2O Solutions (conductometrically) at 298.15 K Using a new Equation for 1:3 Asymmetric Electrolytes : *Journal Chemical engineering data*, Vol. 55, pp 5422-5424.
- [10] Hamada, M. A., Shishtawiand, N. A. E., Gomaa, E. A., (2009), Conductometric Evaluation of Association Constants for Aqueous Solutions of CoCl_2 in the Absence and Presence of a Magnetic Field, *Southern Brazilian : Journal of Chemistry*, Vol.17, pp 33-40.

[11] Gomaa, E. A., (1987), *Solute-Solvent Interactions of Some Univalent-Univalent Salts with Various Organic Solvents at 25°C: Thermochemica Acta, Vol.120, pp 183-189.*

[12] Gomaa, E. A., (1988), *Theoretical Contribution of Solvation of AgBr in Some Organic Solvents at 25°: Thermochemica Acta, Vol. 128, pp 99-120.*

[13] Dossoki, F. I. E., (2008), *Electric Conductance and Semi-Emperical Studies on Two Thiophene Derivatives/Metal Cation Complexation: Journal of Molecular Liquids, Vol. 142, pp 53-56*